

Toward the Standardisation of Annotation Data for Patrimonial Images : Format Issues and Feedback

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Abstract

This article addresses the epistemological and methodological issues of computer vision applied to art historical corpora by highlighting the challenges of use of heterogeneous and diverse formats and tools for annotation. Authors underline the importance of working towards the standardization of patrimonial image annotation by addressing our need for interoperable and reproducible data, in order to fine-tune models for automatic object recognition applied to patrimonial images. The authors advocate that the sharing of these data should be assumed by collaborative endeavors among cultural institutions.

Keywords

Patrimonial images, Segmentation, Annotation, Computer vision, Ground truth, Standards

Introduction

Since Johanna Drucker questioned the existence of a “digital art history” (Drucker 2013), the increasing developments in AI and computer vision have confronted art historians with the need to consider how to adapt and rethink digital art history practices, while critically evaluating them in relation to the specific objects they study and the unique questions they ask.

This necessity is pivotal because dominant computer vision tools have been developed within the context of project-based logic, implemented by private companies, according to technicist and liberal interests, which have benefited from precarious annotation work of massive biased datasets of real-life images (see for example Noble 2018 or D’Ignazio and Klein 2020). These logics have produced top-down approaches, which have been reflected in digital art history practices. They have contributed to the creation of a somewhat fragmented research field, as digital art history projects are often developing their own technical and methodological solutions, which are contingent upon access to substantial financial, human, and temporal resources (Romein and al. 2020: 310).

This necessity is also significant because, whether engaged in large-scale research initiatives or as individual researchers, art historians are encountering similar challenges with computer vision environments and formats, which impact the feasibility of their research and adequacy of their tools. These challenges are produced in part by the inner logic of computer vision methodologies. Indeed, the performance of computer vision models are dependent on the

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annotations used to train them, which determine which features will be detected in the images studied. Art historians thus need to have access to proper annotations and proper models, able to identify specific cultural characteristics and to answer specific research questions. This access is however never guaranteed in practice. Working as PhD candidates in art history on distinctly different tasks, we have indeed found out how often computer vision practices were misaligned with art historians' workflows and methodologies.

To explore these misalignments and potential solutions, we will first address the importance of patrimonial annotation data and motivate the necessity to facilitate its sharing, in contrast to the prevailing siloed methodologies of digital art history (1). Secondly, we will highlight the heterogeneity of the numerous formats and tools available in the computer vision field. We will address the challenges they set by limiting the interoperability of annotation data. To illustrate these challenges, we will go over the case study of layout detection of the contemporary art magazine *Opus International* (2). We will finally identify pathways to explore towards standardizing and sharing annotation data, with the aim of enhancing the integration of computational methodologies and artificial intelligence within digital art history communities (3).

About the Importance of Patrimonial Annotations and their Sharing

Let us begin by recalling the fundamental processes of computer vision: annotation, segmentation, and object detection. These processes involve the grouping of pixels within an image into discrete areas of interest, which are then labelled manually or automatically, and recorded in separate files. The pair of images and their associated files, which contain the coordinates of designated zones and their labels, constitute the annotation data [Figure 1]. Annotations can take the visual form of masks following the contours of the specific elements targeted at the pixel level, in the case of segmentation. It can also take the form of larger bounding boxes framing the targeted element.

Annotation data is employed in the training of models for automatic segmentation or object detection. In the context of transfer learning, annotation data is referred to as "ground truth" and can be employed to refine pre-trained models on new data. As annotation is a challenging and time-consuming process, transfer learning offers numerous advantages, including significant efficiency gains, a reduction in the quantity of data and computational resources, and consequently, a reduction in the number of ground truths (Wasielewski 2023: 103).

It is evident that the field of computer vision has been founded upon extensive datasets and models, including *MS COCO* (Lin et al. 2015) and *ImageNet* (Deng et al. 2009), as well as models such as *YOLO* (Redmon et al. 2016) and *CLIP* (Radford et al. 2021), which are constituted of millions of real-life images. These datasets and models are being used in numerous digital art history projects, as they are the most readily available and accessible. While these datasets and models are undoubtedly efficient, they may nonetheless convey a misaligned, positivist and simplistic understanding of art history corpora. The *MS COCO* dataset is for example designed for object detection according to 80 natural categories, which are evidently insufficient for the rich and complex cultural significance of the images we study.

In order to deploy more nuanced and adequate analysis, art historians have sought to annotate their own datasets and to train more specialized models. The fine-tuning of models derived from hybrid sets of natural and patrimonial annotation has been demonstrated to be an effective approach. However, this approach also presents a discrepancy linked to the 'semantic gap' (Arnold and Tilton 2019: i5) between the objects identified by these models and the cultural

(a) Example of bounding boxes on a page image of *Opus International* in Label Studio.

```

() result.json ×
Users > alicetruc > dev > labelstudio-test > exportCOCO > {} result.json > {} annotations > {} 151
5442 "annotations": [
7708   {
7709     "id": 151,
7710     "image_id": 43,
7711     "category_id": 15,
7712     "segmentation": {},
7713     "bbox": [
7714       180.12828512828517,
7715       136.8974358974359,
7716       770.9487179487181,
7717       79.25641025641022
7718     ],
7719     "ignore": 0,
7720     "iscrowd": 0,
7721     "area": 61102.62787639709
7722   },
7723   {
7724     "id": 152,
7725     "image_id": 43,
7726     "category_id": 3,
7727     "segmentation": {},
7728     "bbox": [
7729       165.7179487179488,
7730       237.76923076923077,
7731       1131.2851282851282,
7732       281.74358974358972
7733     ],
7734     "ignore": 0,
7735     "iscrowd": 0,
7736     "area": 228213.3833004602
7737   },
7738   {
7739     "id": 153,
7740     "image_id": 43,
7741     "category_id": 4,
  
```

(b) Example of the coordinates of the bounding boxes and their labels, recorded in a JSON file in COCO

Figure 1: Examples of annotations of *Opus International*.

meanings that art historians seek to interpret. Firstly, it is important to recognise that patrimonial images do not maintain a direct relationship with the reality of patrimonial objects, as they are not mere copies but always one of their many visual interpretation possible. Furthermore, artworks do not form a homogeneous category of artefacts. The potential objects to be identified are highly diverse, encompassing a range of shapes, colours, and media, as well as varying degrees of interpretation (Panofsky 1939). Their meaning is often not immediately self-evident.

Why are art historians not working directly with specialized patrimonial ground truth and models, which would seem more accurate for their patrimonial corpora ? Using transfer learning in patrimonial projects has been useful, but it has proven not to be an evident process, because of semantic and practical challenges. Firstly, art historians are actually working with much more limited corpora of images than the previously mentioned massive natural datasets. Secondly, patrimonial ground truth is often unavailable for public use or hardly identified on the web. Thirdly and mostly, patrimonial ground truth, the models and tools they have contributed to create, are always interpretative and conceived for specific research goals. It might be difficult to use them from one project to another, since annotation is always an interpretative task, which can hardly be standardized on the semantic level. Each researcher might approach the same material with very different focuses.

The automatic layout detection of the contemporary art review *Opus International* (1967-1995) would for example entail the identification of blocks of text, images, titles, captions, and authors (Figure 1). Alternative approaches to analyzing this material might focus only on the detection of reproductions of paintings or of advertisements. In this case, ground truth with blocks of text and images would be of no use. Conversely, tools trained to detect lines of text in documents (*Arkindex* (Teklia 2023)), to detect specific images (*Cordeep* (Büttner et al. 2022)) or the content of natural scenes (*Segment Anything* Kirillov et al. 2023) would be proven unsuitable for the purpose of automatic layout detection [Figure 2].

Nevertheless, there is value in repurposing ground truth from one project to another when the research question or corpus are sufficiently aligned. Following the work and spirit of the *HTR-United Initiative* (Chagué, Clérice, and Romary 2021), the digital art history community could work towards formalizing homogeneously annotated data in order to make them possible to be shared. Chagué, Clérice and Romary highlight the following:

“We must mention the plasticity of ground truths: it is impossible to merge transcription models, whereas we can assemble, divide, and cross different sets of ground truths to compose a new one.”

Given the diversity of research issues, the plurality of objects of study, and the varying levels of granularity in analyses, the retrieval of ground truths from other projects would facilitate the identification of elements relevant solely to a specific task. It would thus be possible to refine segmentation models to identify different features, depending on the research issues at hand. Furthermore, the ability to access ground truths would enable an understanding of the segmentation practices employed in the creation of a model, if properly documented, and a critical appreciation of its outputs.

Challenges of Computer Vision Tools and Formats : a Case of Layout Detection

Unfortunately, the process of sharing ground truth is not readily implementable in practice. The heterogeneity of formats available in the various computer vision environments and tools fosters

(a) Example of automatic text lign detection of a page in Arkindex.

(b) Example of image recognition with CorDeep, a tool trained on the Sphaera corpus, a collection of first modern textbooks on geocentric cosmology.

(c) Example of object detection with Segmen-Anything.

Figure 2: Examples of misfit use of tools trained on various annotation data, from manuscripts to natural images datasets.

indeed inconsistent annotation practices and datasets, thereby impeding their interoperability. To illustrate these challenges, we will review our past experiments with various computer vision tools using the case study of layout recognition for an art magazine. Published between 1967 and 1995, *Opus International* was launched in Paris as one of the first French contemporary art magazines of a new generation of art critics. The design was initially created by the Polish artist Roman Cieslewicz, who conceived original and artistic layouts inspired by press culture and worked often with *photomontage*. Although the repetitive structure of the review's design and its play of variation from issue to issue lent itself to automatic layout recognition, many technical challenges remained.

At the beginning, our objective was to identify existing generic tools with pre-trained models that could potentially be applied to an art review such as our case of study. For the reasons previously stated, generic tools for the segmentation of patrimonial images are challenging to design. At the time, these tools were, and remain, largely experimental, requiring average to advanced coding skills. Frequently, they were not maintained (*DHSegment*, Oliveira, Seguin, and Kaplan 2018) due to their dependency on libraries, were inadequately and insufficiently documented, making them inaccessible to non-specialists (*Eynollah*, Ahmad et al. 2021), or entailed significant code modifications and adaptations (*Layout-Parser*, Shen et al. 2021).

At a certain point, we resolved to train our own model in order to respond to the specific questions and particularities of the research. The main challenge we faced was then related to the heterogeneity and siloed formats that we encountered in different computer vision tools at each stage of the process. One of the most notable challenges was the fact that each computer vision tool recorded the coordinates and labels of the designed zones of interest in a different way.

This was at first the case with the different popular annotation tools we tried including, for example, *VGG Image Annotator* (Dutta and Zisserman 2019) and *Label Studio* (HumanSignal 2020). To illustrate, on the one hand, the *VGG Image Annotator* tool generates a JSON file comprising a series of x points within the "*allpoints x*" variable and y points within the "*allpoints y*" variable, for a specified region of interest. Conversely, the JSON format of *Label Studio* records each point according to its coordinates in a list. Coordinates and their associated labels can thus be recorded in accordance with the specific logic of each tool, in a heterogeneous and non-hierarchical manner. In order for annotations to be shared and used across different projects, they should be recorded in a format that is easily readable and in accordance with established standards. This approach ensures that the data is interoperable and reproducible.

Typically, annotation tools allow annotations to be exported in a variety of formats. Nevertheless, even more rigorous formats than JSON, such as *ALTO* (Library of Congress 2004) and *PAGE* (Clausner, Antonacopoulos, and Pletschacher 2010), which were designed for textual transcription in structured and controlled XML language, have their own method of recording and displaying the coordinates of detected elements. Furthermore, there are instances where the standardized formats themselves exhibit inconsistencies. To illustrate, the *AbbyFineReader* OCR tool (ABBYY 2019) generates files in its own variant of *ALTO*, which proved incompatible with other tools that were compatible with the generic *ALTO* format.

There are obviously numerous formats within the expansive domain of computer vision which could be employed by digital art history projects. Some of these formats are predominantly used, and it could be postulated that they would be interoperable to a certain extent through conversion tools. The heterogeneity of formats between ground truth and models can nevertheless impact the usability of generic tools and pipelines, even with regard to the prevalent *COCO* format and *YOLO* model. To illustrate, the *COCO* format currently lacks the capacity to manage oriented bounding boxes (OBB), whereas only a *YOLOv8-OBB* version does. Given the potential utility

```
{
  "Nom": "Pétales",
  "Type": "Demi-médaille",
  "Qualité": {
    "good": true,
    "frontal": true,
    "good_illumination": false
  },
  "shape_attributes": {
    "name": "polygon",
    "all_points_x": [
      297, 234, 275, 343, 506, 737, 1033, 1352, 1704, 1985, 2194, 2388, 2472, 2606, 2666, 2684, 2672
    ],
    "all_points_y": [
      1614, 1121, 971, 796, 546, 334, 200, 140, 137, 203, 318, 468, 609, 790, 949, 1111, 1617
    ]
  }
}
```

(a) Example of a VGG Image Annotation annotation file.

```
{
  "id": 3645,
  "annotations": [
    {
      "id": 72,
      "completed_by": 1,
      "result": [
        {
          "original_width": 2800,
          "original_height": 4215,
          "image_rotation": 0,
          "value": {
            "x": 0.5146520146520147,
            "y": 16.41025641025641,
            "width": 99.07051282051283,
            "height": 83.58974358974359,
            "rotation": 0,
            "rectangle_labels": [
              "GraphicZone"
            ]
          },
          "id": "fU49ytfA9q",
          "from_name": "label",
          "to_name": "image",
          "type": "rectangle_labels",
          "origin": "manual"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

(b) Example of a Label Studio annotation file.

Figure 3: Examples of different ways of recording coordinates in annotations with VGG Image Annotator and Label Studio.

of oriented bounding boxes in annotating collections of images with non-aligned features, the incompatibility between these disparate annotation formats and models may result in significant detection errors.

From these experiments, we concluded that the fragmentation of formats represents a significant challenge to the development of a unified, interoperable pipeline for computer vision in digital art history. Despite the importance of such interoperability for advancing research, the lack of standardization across formats hinders research progress. It makes patrimonial annotation data heterogeneous, inconsistent and hard to share and reuse from one project to another. Attempts at creating interoperable pipelines of tools and data for digital art history may sometimes feel like battling to put together pieces of thousand different puzzles.

Figure 4: Example of detection errors linked to mismanaged oriented bounding boxes in annotations.

Pathways to Explore : Toward Standardisation of Annotation Data

As previously stated, standards are already developing and being employed by research communities, particularly in the field of textual research, as exemplified by *ALTO* and *PAGE*, or through the *HTR-United* or *SegmOnto* (Gabay et al. 2023) initiatives. However, these standards are limited to printed and manuscript corpora. Their identification logics correspond to semantic structures conceived by and for textual sources, which are not immediately transposable to patrimonial images. In order to address the question of the standardization of patrimonial annotation data, it is necessary to consider them through an epistemological reasoning about tools and environments. These questions should not be addressed a posteriori from their development, but upstream, in order to accompany the entire process of their production.

One potential solution could be to develop a "cultural heritage" extension for existing computer vision standards, or alternatively, to create conversion tools between different formats. Starting from the research question seems a crucial first step in developing an interoperable format for image annotation. Such a format should remain flexible to accommodate various annotation

techniques, whether bounding boxes, semantic, or panoptic annotations. Additionally, it should capture detailed information about which elements were annotated and how the images were interpreted. The interpretation approach—whether it follows a positive approach or another methodology—also plays a key role in the process of annotation sharing and reuse of ground truth. Ultimately, the development of suitable technical solutions to these challenges would be greatly facilitated by the involvement of GLAMs on a more extensive scale. The aim is to reflect on existing practices to propose sustainable and 'living' tools, driven by research communities to ensure their longevity, evolution, and documentation.

The IIF initiative (International Images Interoperability Framework, 2024[2011]) seems to represent as such an engaging opportunity for rethinking the practices and formats of annotation data within the context of an existing and evolving structure. IIF consists of an interoperability framework designed to disseminate, present, and annotate high-definition images on the web. It has recently become standard practice among cultural and museum institutions to make their collections available and to facilitate online access (Bertrand et al. 2022).

Although not originally intended for this purpose, we posit that IIF could potentially be adapted for the purpose of creating homogeneous annotation data and sharing ground truths associated with images, using ARK identifiers to link annotations directly to high-resolution images without the necessity of republishing the original images. Moreover, as IIF is founded upon the *Web Annotation Data Model* (W3C 2017), which facilitates image annotation and segmentation through the utilization of a dedicated linked standard, it could be adapted to incorporate an interoperable format for their sharing. While it is not a ready-to-use solution for the sharing of patrimonial ground truth and the training of patrimonial models, IIF offers a valuable framework for art historian to consider for the long term¹.

Conclusion

A number of studies have recently challenged the refinement of computer vision models when applied to patrimonial corpora (see for example Cai and al. 2015; Lang and Ommer 2018; Hiipapala 2021 and Shen et al. 2021). The responses provided are diverse but predominantly concentrate on the refinement of models and transfer learning from large generic models trained on natural images. However, these models are not designed to account for the specific epistemological and methodological requirements of annotation in the field of heritage. In order to engage a critical reflection on the practices and tools employed in the field of computer vision, with regard to patrimonial collections, it is imperative to center the question of standardization of homogeneous and interoperable annotation data.

Two points appear to be essential. Firstly, it is crucial to recognise that these corpora cannot be treated in the same manner as natural images. It is imperative that the cultural, symbolic value and historicity of these images are not overlooked. Secondly, it is essential to consider how public access to standardized annotation data can be facilitated, enabling its reuse for the improvement of new models. The objective is to circumvent the silo dynamics that prevent the sharing of ground truths, with the aim of developing more efficient models for automatic detection in patrimonial images. While projects such as IIF offer valuable inspiration, the adaptation of its framework to create a standard for annotation data would necessitate the involvement of collective groups of experts, including data engineers, digital humanists and art historians, museal professionals, librarians and archivists. It is essential to engage GLAMs

¹The potential of using IIF to share annotations and to, more broadly, streamline workflows in digital art history have been further explored in another article (Maronet and Truc, To be published)

on a larger scale in the future, to lead digital art history practices towards more integrated, historically and critically accurate computer vision practices within research communities.

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